

FABRICATION AND TESTING OF SMART FRP REINFORCEMENTS

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SUMMARY: The aspects of fabrication, microstructural evaluation and experimental testing of smart composites are discussed. The technology for the fabrication of fiber reinforced polymer composites with embedded optical fibers is developed. Smart composites are produced by a custom built pultruder. The pultruded carbon reinforced rods with and without optical fiber showed higher shear and tensile strength, as well as greater tensile modulus than did the glass fiber analogue. The embedded optical fibers do not have significant effect on the tensile properties of pultruded rods, but they slightly affected the shear strength of the glass fiber rods. Polyimide coating on optical fiber results in a good interface between optical fiber and host material; whereas acrylate coating cannot withstand the high production temperature and causes severe debonding of optical fiber and resin.

KEYWORDS: smart fiber reinforced polymer composites, pultrusion, optical fiber sensors, tensile and shear strength, interface debonding

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have recently been used in civil engineering structures, including monitoring, rehabilitation projects, prestressing tendons, reinforcing bars, and most recently as innovative structural members of bridges [1, 2]. For these reasons, composite materials lend themselves as prime candidates for another rapidly expanding field of research known as "smart materials". A smart material is a structure which contains a built in sensing device to continuously monitor the current state and serviceability of the structure. This is referred to as a "passive" smart material which has many applications in civil engineering. Composite materials are good candidates as smart materials because their "build up" fabrication techniques inherently allow for the embedment of sensors and communication lines.

To date, the hand layup in combination with vacuum bagging and autoclaving has been most often used to fabricate smart composites. This can be a labour intensive and time-consuming process in which the quality of the final product is significantly affected by the skill and experience of the technician. Pultrusion, which is the only continuous process, has received little attention in the area of smart composites, and there are currently only a few published papers on this subject [3, 4]. However, by considering the costs and cycle times which are favorable criteria for selection of a manufacturing process, pultrusion is the fastest and most cost effective process. For engineering applications, pultrusion is also well suited to produce prestressing tendons and reinforcing bars, because it can provide the structures with a high degree of axial reinforcement. A part of the work reported here concerns the adaptation of pultrusion techniques into a manufacturing process for smart composite reinforcements.

The diameter of an optical fiber is typically much larger than the diameter of a reinforcing fiber. Thus, when embedding large diameter optical fibers in a composite, some loss of strength of the composite could occur because of optical fiber induced stress and strain concentrations in the host material. The degradation in the mechanical properties of the composite is also related to some other factors, such as the position of the optical fiber within a composite and the bond strength of the optical fiber and host material. The location of an optical fiber within a product may affect the mechanical properties, as well as the sensing capability of the smart materials. Also to be considered is the interface between the optical fiber and host material. To effectively transfer strain from the resin matrix to an embedded fiber optic sensor, a good bond of the optical fiber to host material is required. In general, optical fibers are protected with a buffer coating for increased durability. The bond strength of the optical fiber and host material is therefore dependent upon the characteristics of the buffer coating, i.e. its ability to survive in the harsh composite production environment and its chemical compatibility with the resin matrix system used to produce the composite.

The objective of this research is to develop a continuous manufacturing process for embedding optical fiber and sensors in fiber reinforced plastic composites, and to determine how the embedment of optical fibers and their surface coatings affect the mechanical properties of the composite materials. To achieve these objectives, a microstructural analysis was carried out on both the pultruded profile's cross section, and fracture surfaces obtained from mechanically fractured samples. This analysis was carried out in order to verify the quality of the pultruded composites and to look at the interfaces between optical fibers and host materials.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The resin system which was used for all of the pultrusion tests in this study was a urethane modified bisphenol vinylester. The resin was chosen for its excellent mechanical properties, as well as its low viscosity and high pulling speeds. Two kinds of organic peroxide catalysts were required to cure the resin, and the adequate release from the mold was achieved using an internal lubricant.

Both glass fiber and carbon fiber reinforcements were used to produce composite materials for this study. The sizing on both types of fibers is stated by the manufacturers as being compatible with a vinylester resin system.

Two types of optical fibers were also used for this research. The first was a polyimide-coated single mode optical fiber. Its overall diameter was 155 microns with a 10 micron core and a 125 micron cladding. The second optical fiber was a multimode fiber with an overall diameter of 250 microns, a 50 micron core, and a 125 micron cladding. This fiber contained a UV cured acrylate surface coating.

Processing of Pultruded Rod Samples

In this study, 9.5 mm diameter rod stock was produced using a customized pultrusion machine which was designed and constructed at the Smart Materials Centre of the Technical University of Nova Scotia [1]. This machine is shown schematically in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of laboratory scale pultrusion system.

Reinforcing fibers (E-glass or carbon rovings) were pulled from a creel system, via a resin tank containing vinylester resin, into a shaping die. The fibers are thoroughly wetted with resin in the dipping tank and polymerization (an exothermic chemical reaction) takes place in an electrically heated die at temperatures of up to 150°C. A rigid cured profile corresponding to the die shape was pulled from the die by a caterpillar pulling system at a constant rate, which for this study was 30 cm/min. Materials produced at higher pulling speeds are not reported at this time. The finished products were cut to the desired length by a cut off saw.

During the production of the pultruded rods, one or two optical fibers were placed at an intended location within the composite with the aid of a positioning device, which was firmly fixed at the entrance to the die.

Both visual inspections and optical microscopy were used as an early quality assessment evaluation for all of the pultruded products.

Mechanical Testing and Microscopic Examination

The tensile and shear properties of the pultruded rods were carried out in accordance with ASTM D3916 and ASTM D4475 respectively, on a hydraulically driven MTS Model 8504RM testing machine using Instron series IX software.

A stereo microscope was used to examine the pultruded profile's cross section and to determine the location of the optical fiber(s). To facilitate this examination, a cross section of each rod was ground on silicon carbide abrasive papers with grit sizes ranging from 120 to 800 microns. The rods were examined at magnifications ranging from 10x to 20x.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed on various polished cross sections, as well as on the fracture surfaces from rods which had been subjected to mechanical testing. A Jeol JSM 820 SEM was used to study the interfaces between optical fibers and host materials, as well as the presence of delaminations or voids, in the polished rod sections. A Jeol JXA35 SEM was used to examine fiber pull-out and fiber-matrix debonding in the fractured rod samples. To prepare the samples for the SEM, the ground samples were polished on with 3 and 1 micron diamond suspensions, as well as colloidal silica. A 20 nm gold/palladium coating was applied to each sample via a hummer X sputtering coater.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pultrusion Processing Equipment

A large quantity of glass and carbon fiber reinforced vinylester rods with and without the embedded optical fiber was fabricated using the laboratory scale pultrusion machine. This pultrusion machine was successful at producing very consistent products. The pultruder shows certain improved performance as compared to the conventional analogue. For example, the specialized fiber feed system is capable of locating the optical fiber with high precision; the caterpillar pulling system which is driven by a DC motor gives highly accurate speed control at less than 0.1 % variation, and at a constant pulling force; and the desktop work platform as well as being portable and modular, provides easy access to the entire work area.

Fig. 2: SEM micrograph shows excellent interface between polyimide coated optical fiber and host material (500 x).

Furthermore, it is capable of pulling speeds of up to 36 inches per minute. This is virtually in good agreement with the statement that pultrusion is the fastest and most cost effective process for fabricating composites as compared to other processes. The verification of other required processing parameters such as temperature control revealed that the customized pultruder has performed satisfactorily according to design specification. Temperature was controlled on 3 separate zones along the length of the die, in order to obtain the required

curing profiles for the vinyl ester resin. Setup of the pultrusion line was made simpler and faster as the system was designed in order to achieve self alignment of the die with the pulling mechanism.

Survivability of Optical Fibers in Pultrusion Process

Previous studies have reported that polyimide coated fibers have a melting point of 385°C, and therefore possess a superior ability to withstand high temperatures [5]. These fibers were thus expected to survive the cure temperatures encountered in the pultrusion process. They were also chemically compatible with resin matrix used, and hence created good interface with host material. Fig. 2 is an SEM micrograph which illustrates that our results were very consistent with the above statements in that the polyimide coated fiber has survived the pultrusion process, and appears to be well bonded to the resin matrix.

Fig. 3: SEM micrograph shows debonding between acrylate-coated optical fiber and host material (250 x).

It has also been reported that the acrylate coating on common optical fibers could not withstand processing temperatures greater than 85°C [5]. In the current study, the maximum curing temperature was 150°C. Therefore, the acrylate coating was not expected to survive in this harsh production environment. This was supported by the evidence, as shown in the SEM micrograph of Fig. 3. Severe debonding between the acrylate coated optical fiber and the host material occurred, most likely due to melting and distortion of the acrylate coating. For this reason, the majority of the work reported in this study involves an investigation of the embedment of polyimide coated optical fibers within pultruded composites.

Comparison of Pultruded Carbon and Glass FRP Rods

Casual visual inspection of the pultruded carbon and glass reinforced rods indicated some common features. All of the pultruded rods had a consistently circular shape and excellent surface finish. The embedded optical fiber in the cross section of the glass FRP rod was easily visible by eye. However, the location of the optical fiber in carbon FRP required an optical microscope with good lighting.

The mechanical properties of pultruded carbon and glass reinforced composites are given in Table 1. A comparison of tensile properties of these two kinds of pultruded rods is presented in Fig. 4, from which the large difference between the tensile strengths of carbon and glass fiber reinforced samples was observed regardless of the presence of optical fibers. As expected, the use of carbon fiber gave much higher tensile strength (1245 MPa) than glass reinforcement (902 MPa). This is because the fibers are the principal load-carrying agent and in a fiber reinforced unidirectional composite, the properties such as strength and modulus in the fiber direction are fiber-dominated [6]. The inherent tensile strength of carbon fiber is about 64% greater than that of E-glass. The tensile failure modes of all the samples were typical fiber breakage and debonding.

In view of the results in Table 2, the shear strengths of the pultruded rods appear to be insensitive to the type of fiber reinforcement. In principle, the short beam shear test is designed to determine the interfacial adhesion of the resin and fiber, and the strength of the matrix [7, 8]. Both glass and carbon fibers used in this study had been treated with a surface sizing, which is compatible with vinylester resin. Thus similarly good interfaces between

Table 1. Tensile properties of fiber-reinforced vinylester composites

Material	Strength (MPa)	Standard Deviation (MPa)	Tensile Modulus (MPa)	Standard Deviation (MPa)
Glass FRP				
No optical fiber	902	126	48.2	1.1
One polyimide fiber	949	55	47.3	0.7
Carbon FRP				
No optical fiber	1245	118	140.8	
One optical fiber	1246	56	144.2	3.4

Table 2. Shear properties of fiber-reinforced vinylester composites

Material	Shear Strength (MPa)	Standard Deviation (MPa)
Glass FRP		
No optical Fiber	29.3	1.3
One polyimide fiber	27.2	1.1
Two polyimide fibers	25.4	1.0
One acrylate fiber	29.2	2.2
Carbon FRP		
No optical fiber	29.7	1.6
One polyimide fiber	29.5	1.5

these two kinds of fiber reinforcements and vinylester resin within the pultruded rod would be expected. Thus, the shear strength of a pultruded composite in this case is virtually given by the resin matrix. However, it is important to note that embedding an optical fiber into the pultruded part slightly affected the mean shear strength of the glass fiber reinforced composites, as can be seen from Table 2. The reason to be considered for this will be given in the following section.

Effect of Optical Fiber Embeddement on the Mechanical Properties of Smart Materials

Fig. 4 illustrates that the tensile strength and modulus of glass and carbon fiber pultruded FRP rods were virtually unaffected by the embeddement of a single polyimide coated optical fiber. Earlier publications [5,9] also reported that an embedded optical fiber did not have a detrimental influence on tensile properties when embedded in the same direction as the composite's reinforcing fibers. The suggested explanation is that the fiber reinforcement is the only significant factor directly affecting the tensile properties of unidirectional composite [6]. Fig. 5 shows the effect of an embedded optical fiber on the mean shear strength of fiber reinforced vinylester composites. The embedded optical fiber had a total diameter of 155 microns and had a polyimide coating. As the number of the embedded optical fibers increased from 0 through 1 to 2, the mean shear strength of glass FRP rod decreased by 11% and 17% respectively, from 29.9 MPa through 26.9 MPa to 25.6 MPa. Pultruded carbon fiber reinforced rods appeared not to be affected by the presence of a single embedded polyimide coated optical fiber. The mean shear strength values were virtually identical. The shear strength of the carbon rod with an optical fiber (29.5 MPa) was less than 1% lower than the shear strength of the baseline carbon rod with no optical fiber (29.7 MPa). However, this difference falls within the standard deviation of the data obtained for the baseline rod. While the mean strength reduction of 11-17% in the glass FRP rods containing optical fibers appears to be real, and outside of the standard deviation for the baseline rods, it should also be stated that the scatter in the data obtained from the short beam shear test is in the range of 10-15% as well. Increasing the number of samples from 5 to 10 for each test category reaffirmed the reduction in mean shear strength.

Fig. 4: Comparison of tensile properties of pultruded CFRP and GFRP rods.

Fig. 5: Comparison of shear properties of pultruded CFRP and GFRP rods.

The degradation in the shear strength is caused by the changes induced by the optical fiber on a micro level within the pultruded composite. It has been reported that the incorporation of optical fibers with a comparatively large diameter of 155 microns, although the embedments were placed in the direction of the reinforcing fiber, may cause the formation of resin-rich regions near the fiber-matrix interface [10]. This effect causes internal material geometry variations in the vicinity of interfaces [11]. This resulted in a large strain concentration, which in turn caused the premature failure of the composite under shear stress. In support of this theory, the quantitative micromechanical analysis and measurement of the strain concentrations caused by embedded fibers were conducted [12]. The results in that study showed that an applied load equal to half the failure load of the eight-ply specimens tested, generated a strain of approximately 0.05 at the fiber-matrix interface.

Adding two optical fibers into the pultruded rod had a more significant effect on the shear strength of glass FRP than did a single optical fiber embedment, see Fig. 5. The obvious reason for this can be inferred from the above discussion. Also, this result is consistent with a previous publication [13], stating that large numbers of embedded optical fibers had a more pronounced influence upon the compressive properties (matrix-dominated properties) of laminates, than did smaller numbers.

In the case of carbon FRP rods, a single embedded optical fiber did not have any noticeable effect on the shear strength, see Fig. 5. The optical fiber having less significant effect on the shear strength of carbon FRP rod was, in this case, thought to be attributed to a good bond strength between carbon fiber and vinyl ester resin [1]. Another interesting factor to be considered is the failure behaviour of the specimens under shear stress. After testing, fracture surfaces were carefully monitored and found to be away from the location of the optical fiber embedded in a rod in the cases of a polyimide coating. At the same time, in the cases of acrylate coated optical fibers, the fracture surface passed through the interface of optical fiber.

Fig. 6: Optical micrograph shows a cross section of the pultruded Glass FRP rod with two embedded optical fibers (14 x)

It is also interesting to note that the mean shear strength of the pultruded glass FRP rod containing an embedded acrylate coated optical fiber was slightly higher than that for the baseline rod. The acrylate coated optical fiber was expected to deteriorate the mechanical properties of the pultruded glass FRP rod due to its large overall diameter of 250 microns, and because it had failed to survive the pultrusion process, as was shown earlier in Fig. 3. It was also expected to produce mechanical property values that were lower than those for rods containing embedded polyimide optical fibers which were smaller, and had survived the high temperatures of the pultrusion process.

Fig. 7: Variation in relative fiber position of two optical fibers in Glass FRP rod shown in Fig. 6.

Microscopic Analysis

A cross section of a glass FRP rod containing two embedded optical fibers is shown in Fig. 6. The optical fibers are located inside the rod at a fixed distance apart, as determined by the positioning device in the fiber feed system. Fig. 7 illustrates the variation in the distance between the two optical fibers, as determined over an embedded distance of 10 m. It can thus be seen that an embedded optical fiber exhibits little wander or drift inside the composite rod, with a maximum deviation of 0.5 mm from a specific location over a 10 m span.

The absence of delaminations or voids in Fig. 6 appears to indicate that the pultruded rods are of good quality.

CONCLUSIONS

The pultrusion process for the fabrication of FRP smart materials has been successfully set up at Smart Materials Centre at the Technical University of Nova Scotia. The positioning of optical fibers and sensors within a composite was achieved by using a specially designed locating device. Polyimide coating on optical fiber results in a good interface between optical fiber and host material; whereas acrylate coating cannot withstand the harsh environment (high production temperature) and causes severe debonding of optical fiber and resin. Therefore, polyimide-coated optical fiber should be a preferential selection to be used in this study. Embedded optical fibers do not have a significant effect on the tensile properties of the pultruded FRP, but they slightly deteriorate the shear strength of composites. This slight decrease in shear strength was seen for the glass rods, but was not evident in the carbon rods. As the number of embedded optical fibers in the composite is increased, the effect upon the shear strength is also increased.

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REFERENCES

1. Kalamkarov, A.L., Yang, Q., MacDonald, D.O. and Westhaver, P.A.D., "Experimental applications of smart composites", *International Conference on Experimental Mechanics: Advances and Applications (ICEM'96)*, Singapore, Abstracts: p. 40, December 1996, Proceedings in press.
2. MacDonald D.O. and Kalamkarov, A.L., "On the application of pultruded smart composites in civil engineering", *Proc. of the Third International Conference on Composites Engineering*, 1996, pp. 549-550.
3. Friebele, E., Askins, C., Putnam, M., Florio, J., Fasha, A., Donti, R. and Mosley, C., "Distributed strain sensing with fiber Bragg grating arrays embedded in CRTM™ composites", *SPIE Vol. 2361, 2nd European Conference on Smart Structure and Materials*, 1994, pp. 338-341.

4. Friebele, E.J., Askins, C.G., Putnam, M.A., William, G.M., Kersey, A.D., Fosha, Jr., A.A., Florio, Jr., J., Donti, R.P. and Blosser, R.G., "Fabrication and application of low-cost optical fiber sensor arrays for industrial and commercial applications", *Industrial and Commercial Appl. of Smart Structures Tech., SPIE*, Vol. 2447, Crowe, C.R. and Anderson, G.L., Eds., 1995, pp. 305-311.
5. Leka, L. and Bayo, E., "A close look at the embedment of optical fibers into composite structures", *Journal of Composites Technology & Research*, Vol. 11, No. 3, 1989, pp. 106-112.
6. Kalamkarov, A.L., *Composite and Reinforced Elements of Construction*, John Wiley & Sons, Chichester, New-York, 1992.
7. English, L.K., "Composite materials-special report", *Materials Engineering*, September 1987, pp. 15-50.
8. Kubel, E., "Advanced materials star at SAMPE", *Materials Engineering*, June 1985, pp. 63-66.
9. Measures, R.M., Glossop, N.D.W., Lymer, J. and Tennyson, R.C., "Structurally integrated fiber optic damage assessment system for composite materials", *Proc. SPIE*, Vol. 986, 1988, pp. 120-129.
10. Udd, E., "Overview of fiber optic smart structures for aerospace applications", *Proc. SPIE*, Vol. 986, 1988, pp. 2-5.
11. Measures, R.M., Glossop, N.D.W., Lymer, J., West, J., Tsaw, W. and Tennyson, R.C., "Fibre optic impact damage detection of composite Materials", *Fibre Optics 88, Proc. SPIE*, 1988, pp. 949-952.
12. Czarnek, R., Guo, Y., Bennett, K.D. and Claus, R.O., "Interferometric measurements of strain concentrations induced by an optical fiber embedded in fiber reinforced composites", *Proc. SPIE*, Vol. 986, 1988, pp. 43-54.
13. Jensen, D. and Pascual, J., "Degradation of graphite/bismaleimide laminates with multiple embedded fiber-optic sensors", *Proc. SPIE*, Vol. 1370: Fiber Optic Smart Structures and Skins III, 1990, pp 228-237.